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CORRECTION AND TACTICS OF PREGNANCY ADMINISTRATION IN CASE OF VIOLATIONS OF THE VAGINAL ECOSYSTEM

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ANNOTATION

Bacterial vaginosis arises when the usual vaginal flora is replaced by opportunistic microorganisms. This condition can be asymptomatic or present with clinical signs; a pH level exceeding 4.5 and an increased count of opportunistic bacteria may suggest bacterial vaginosis. During pregnancy, bacterial vaginosis complicates the existing health issues and heightens the risk of miscarriage and premature delivery. Pregnant individuals with bacterial vaginosis are at a greater risk for developing chorioamnionitis and postpartum endometritis.

Keywords: vagina, opportunistic infections, inflammatory, Candida albicans, microbial population.

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КОРРЕКЦИЯ И ТАКТИКА ВВЕДЕНИЯ БЕРЕМЕННОСТИ ПРИ НАРУШЕНИЙ ЭКОСИСТЕМЫ ВЛАГАЛИЩА

АННОТАЦИЯ

В последние десятилетия оппортунистические инфекции, вызываемые условно-патогенными микроорганизмами, заняли особое место в практике клиницистов различных специальностей. Во многих странах мира, в том числе и в Узбекистане, наблюдается рост вагинальных инфекций, которые прочно занимают ведущее место в структуре акушерской и гинекологической заболеваемости.

Ключевые слова: влагалище, оппортунистические инфекции, воспаление, Candida albicans, микробная популяция.

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ЕКТОТИЗИМ БУЗИЛИШИ КУЗАТИЛГАН ГОМИЛАДОРЛАРДА ГОМИЛАДОРЛИКНИ ОЛИБ БОРИШ ТАКТИКАСИ ВА КРРЕКСИЯСИ

ANNOTATSIYA

So'nggi o'n yilliklarda opportunistik patogenlar keltirib chiqaradigan opportunistik infektsiyalar turli mutaxassislar amaliyotida alohida o'rin egalladi. Dunyoning ko'plab mamlakatlarida, shu jumladan O'zbekistonda, akusherlik va ginekologik kasalliklar tarkibida etakchi o'rinni egallagan vaginal infektsiyalarning ko'payishi kuzatilmoqda. Qin mikroflorasining tarkibining buzilishi bir qancha asoratlarga sabab bo'lishi mumkin.

Kalit so'zlar: qin, opportunistik infektsiyalar, yallig'lanish, Candida albicans, mikroblar populyatsiyasi.

Purpose of the Study. The aim of this research is to evaluate the importance of measuring vaginal pH in women at risk of miscarriage.

Relevance: Disruption of the vaginal ecosystem during early pregnancy can lead to complications such as late miscarriages, premature births, intrauterine and postpartum infections, inflammatory diseases after childbirth, and unintended pregnancies. This disruption often results in a reduction or complete loss of lactobacilli in the vaginal flora. The significance of this issue in obstetrics is compounded by the often asymptomatic nature of bacterial vaginosis (BV) in pregnant women, making diagnosis challenging due to the absence of specific symptoms.

Materials and Methods: The study was conducted at a family clinic in Samarkand, involving 46 pregnant women receiving outpatient treatment for threatened miscarriage. Inclusion criteria included being under 22 weeks pregnant, no bleeding during the study, and providing informed consent. Exclusion criteria included being over 22 weeks, having bloody discharge, multiple pregnancies, uterine abnormalities, diabetes, hypertension, cervical insufficiency, HIV, hepatitis B and C, and recent use of spermicides, antiseptics, or antibiotics. All participants consented and were informed about the study's goals and design. Data collected included patient complaints, medical history (general and obstetric-gynecological), physical examination results, and laboratory tests. Special focus was placed on identifying chronic infection sites in the genitourinary system and other organs, as well as the use of hygiene products. Vaginal pH was measured in all participants using "Kolpo-test pH" test strips from Biosensor AN, Russia. Statistical analysis was performed using nonparametric methods via Statistica 6.1, and the significance of differences was assessed with the Chi-square test at $p < 0.05$.

Results and Discussion: The average age of participants was 28.9 years (ranging from 21 to 39), with 13 (23.2%) over 30 years old. Among the participants, 22 (47.8%) were primigravidas and 24 (52.2%) were multigravidas, with 15 (62.5%) of the multigravidas having a history of childbirth. The study indicated that over 65% of participants exhibited abnormalities in vaginal pH. Three groups were formed based on pH levels: Group 1 (n=18) with normocenosis, Group 2 (n=11) with mycotic vaginitis, and Group 3 (n=17) with vaginal dysbiosis. Nearly half of the participants showed alkalization, indicating BV. Among those, 10 patients (58.8%) reported homogeneous watery discharge, while 7 (41.2%) had no complaints, suggesting an asymptomatic course of BV in about one-third of participants with pH disturbances. Complaints of white cheesy discharge, itching, and burning were reported by 9 pregnant women (81.8%) in Group 2.

Additionally, 28 participants had a complicated obstetric and gynecological history, with 35.8% (n=10) in Group 1, 14.2% (n=4) in Group 2, and 50% (n=14) in Group 3. Frequent use of intimate hygiene products was noted among 34 participants: 55.5% (n=10) in Group 1, 72.7% (n=8)

in Group 2, and 59.3% (n=16) in Group 3. Furthermore, 32 women had chronic infections in the genitourinary system, while only 17 had chronic infections in other organs.

In Group 1, most patients had a smear purity grade of 3, while Group 2 predominantly had grade 4. In Group 3, most patients had grade 3 smear purity, with fewer at grade 4 and only 7.4% at grade 2.

Research indicates that dysbiotic disorders of vaginal microbiocenosis play a significant role in pregnancy complications, with recurrent dysbiosis potentially impacting cervical structure, leading to asymptomatic shortening and increasing the risk of premature birth and low-birth-weight infants. Determining vaginal pH can serve as an early diagnostic method for microflora disorders in both outpatient and inpatient gynecological settings.

An analysis of pregnancy outcomes revealed that measuring vaginal pH in women at risk of miscarriage reduced preterm birth rates by 23.3% (from 30.0% to 6.7%). In the control group, where pH testing was not conducted, the preterm birth rate was 19.4% (initially 22.2%). The first trimester is identified as the ideal time for screening intrauterine infections and dysbiotic conditions in the vagina and cervical canal, allowing for timely treatment and prevention of complications during pregnancy and postpartum.

Conclusions: The high prevalence of BV among pregnant women at risk of miscarriage underscores the necessity of incorporating vaginal pH measurement into examination protocols. This method is straightforward, accessible, and cost-effective, making it suitable as a screening test for early detection of vaginal microflora disorders. Routine pH testing can facilitate timely identification of vaginal dysbiosis and appropriate management of the identified conditions.

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